

6th International Conference on Networks & Communications (NWCOM 2020)
October 24-25, 2020, Sydney, Australia
<https://csity2020.org/nwcom/index.html>

Scope

6th International Conference on Networks & Communications (NWCOM 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology. The Conference looks for significant contributions to all major fields of the Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology in theoretical and practical aspects.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to.

Topics of Interest

- Adhoc and sensor networks
- Heterogeneous wireless networks
- High speed networks
- Internet and Web applications
- Measurement & Performance Analysis
- Mobile & Broadband Wireless Internet
- Mobile Communications and Telematics
- Mobile networks & Wireless LAN
- Network Architectures
- Network Based applications
- Network Operations & management
- Network Protocols & Wireless Networks
- Network Security
- Next Generation Internet
- Next Generation Web Architectures
- Peer to peer and overlay networks
- QoS and Resource Management
- Recent trends & Developments in Computer Networks
- Routing, switching and addressing techniques
- Self-Organizing Networks and Networked Systems
- Ubiquitous networks
- Wireless communications
- Wireless Multimedia systems

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission system](#) by **July 11, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **NWCOM 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journals

- [International Journal of Computer Networks & Communications \(IJCNC\)](#) - ERA Indexed, Scopus Indexed
- [International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications \(IJNSA\)](#) - ERA Indexed
- [International Journal of Wireless & Mobile Networks \(IJWMN\)](#) - ERA Indexed
- [International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology \(IJWesT\)](#) - IS Indexed
- [International Journal of UbiComp \(IJU\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)](#)^{New} - ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : July 11, 2020**
- Authors Notification : September 11, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : September 19, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : nwcom@csity2020.org or nwcomcon@yahoo.com